

Women's Empowerment: A Study of Challenges and the Constitutional Initiative for Women's Empowerment

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The social and political human behavior are invariably dependent on each other and in this process human relations takes a course of trajectory with the views of difference in gender understanding. Though the social fabric of India is knitted along the corridor of distinct caste groups. In general it is understood that the women deity are viewed with reverence but in reality the girl child are not treated equal to the boy child. Caste functions sociologically as a uniting factor of masses but in a subtle manner discriminates women as a gender of burden, when a question of marriage and other factor arises. The factors that affect women mostly are their liberty and freedom. Despite the growth of feminist attributes, the growth of women in general are invariably affected by the issues that are not addressed clearly favoring the needs and demands of women. The dynamics of society keeps changing but with not much of any assertion in the rights of women. The researcher intends to understand how state society and politics invariably affect the growth and development of women. Caste breeds hatred violence and discrimination and in the process women are placed on the cross fire. Proliferation of sex determination test labs, lack of interest in giving education for girl children, gender bias in employment and in work places the problems women undergo are few gender and caste based problems. Researcher try to assess the lasting impact the women empowerment movement has made on women and their rights.

Historical Background of Women Empowerment in India

The Status of Women in India has undergone several changes over the past few decades. It is believed that during early vedic period Women enjoyed equal status with men. Rigved and upanishads had mentioned several names of women sages . However the status of women began to deteriorate around 500 B.C and the situation worsened with invasion of Mughals and European invaders. Some reformatory movements by Guru Nanak, Jainism, Rajaram mohan

Rai, Ishwarchandra Vidya Sagar, Pandita Rama Bai and others made significant effort in reforming the society. British rule brought some laws such as “Abolition of practice of Sati” and Widow Remarriage Act 1856. The real change happened after independence. Constitution of India guarantees equality to women to ensure rights of women to enjoy equal opportunity in every sphere of their life.¹

India’s effort for Women Empowerment

The constitution ensured that the Principle of Gender Equality is enshrined in the Indian Constitution in its Preamble, Fundamental duties and Directive Principles. Constitution also empowers the states to adopt measures of positive discrimination in favour of women.

The movement gained impetus when Mrs. Indira Gandhi, launched a scheme known as Indira Mahila Yojana. UNDP also included issues of women upliftment as Primary objective. Various Schemes were later on launched for the empowerment of women such as Rashriya Mahila Kosh and Mahila Samridhi Yojana at Panchyat level. The establishment of National Women’s Commission and State Women’s Commissions were important milestones in the direction of Women Empowerment in India.²

The National Policy for the Empowerment of women was an important step taken by the Government of India for accelerating women empowerment process. The policy was aimed to ensure women empowerment through economic and social policies for the development of women. The policy assured equal access to women to health care, quality education, participation and in decision making.³

Challenges before women in India

The challenges that affects women’s right in India are assessed in the following passages.

Education

While studying the literacy rate, the gap between women and men is acute. While 82.14% of adult men are educated, only 65.46% of adult women are known to be literate in India. The gender bias in higher education and in specialized professional trainings affect women in employment and as well in attaining top leadership in the field where women are associated with.

Poverty

Due to abject poverty, women are exploited as domestic helps and servants and their incomes being usurped indicates the living condition of women in the society. Due to gender bias in health and nutrition there is unusually high mortality rate in women which had reduced women population drastically in Asia, Africa and China.⁴

Health and Safety

UNICEF came up with the details on the status of new mothers in India in its 2009 report. The maternal mortality report of India stands at 301 per 1000, with as many as 78000 women in India dying of childbirth complications in that year. Today, due to the population explosion, the number has multiplied considerably. Despite several programmes created by the Government and several NGO’s in the country, there is still a wide gap that exist to be addressed

Household Inequality

All across the globe house hold relations indicates the existence of gender bias and as well in India. Childcare house work, menial work are few examples to quote. Such inequalities are not adequately addressed and redressed world over.⁵

India's initiative for the women empowerment

The constitution Framers were very much conscious of the problem of women empowerment hence they ensured that the Principle of Gender Equality is enshrined in the Indian Constitution in its Preamble, Fundamental duties and Directive Principles. The various articles mentioned in the earlier paragraph are meant for ensuring gender equality. Moreover the Constitution also empowers the states to adopt measures of positive discrimination in favour of women. The real impetus for this movement gained when the Prime minister of India Mrs. Indira Gandhi, launched a scheme known as Indira Mahila Yojana. UNDP also incorporated issues of women upliftment as Primary objective. Various Schemes were later on launched for the empowerment of women such as Rashtriya Mahila Kosh, Mahila Samridhi Yojana, Self help groups at Panchayat level and many more. The establishment of National Women's Commission and State Women's Commissions were important milestones in the direction of women empowerment in India.⁶

Constitutional Provisions for Women

The Constitution of India granted equality to women and empowered the State to take special measures of positive discrimination to eliminate the disadvantages faced by the women in the society. Certain articles in Indian constitution pertaining to the women empowerment are highlighted below.⁷

- (1) Equality before law of women (Article 14)
- (2) The State not to discriminate against any citizen on grounds only of religion, race, caste, sex, place of birth or any of them (Article 15 (i))
- (3) The State to make any special provision in favour of women and children (Article 15(3))
- (4) Equality of opportunity for all citizens in matters relating to employment or appointment to any office under the State (Article 16)
- (5) The State to direct its policy towards securing for men and women equally the right to an adequate means of livelihood (Article 39(a)); and equal pay for equal work for both men and women (Article 39(d))
- (6) To promote justice, on a basis of equal opportunity and to provide free legal aid by suitable legislation or scheme or in any other way to ensure that opportunities for securing justice are not denied to any citizen by reason economic or other disabilities (Article 39A)
- (7) The State to make provision for securing just and humane conditions of work and for maternity relief (Article 42)
- (8) The State to promote with special care the educational and economic interests of the weaker sections of the people and to protect them from social injustice and all forms of exploitation (Article 47)
- (9) The State to raise the level of nutrition and the standard of living of its people (Article 47)
- (10) To promote harmony and the spirit of common brotherhood amongst all the people of India and to renounce practices derogatory to the dignity of women (Article 51(A)(e))
- (11) Not less than one-third including the number of seats reserved for women belonging to the scheduled Castes and the Scheduled Tribes of the total number of seats to be filled by direct election in every Panchayat to be reserved for women and such seats to be allotted by rotation to different constituencies in a Panchayat (Article 243 D(3))
- (12) Not less than one-third of the total number of offices of Chairpersons in the Panchayats at each level to be reserved for women (Article 243 D (4))
- (13) Not less than one-third (including the number of seats reserved for women belonging to the Scheduled castes and the Scheduled Tribes) of the total number of seats to be filled by direct election in every Municipality to be reserved for women and such seats to be allotted by rotation to different constituencies in a Municipality.

(14) Reservation of offices of chairpersons in Municipalities for the Scheduled Castes, the scheduled Tribes and women in such manner as the legislature of a state may by law provide.⁸

Special initiatives for Women empowerment

Nation commission for women empowerment (January 1992):

The Government had set-up this statutory body with a specific mandate to study and monitor all matters relating to the constitutional and legal safeguards provided for women, review the existing legislation to suggest necessary amendments

Women empowerment in local self-government:

The 73rd constitutional acts passed in 1992 by parliament ensure one-third of the total seats for women in all elected offices in local bodies whether in rural areas or urban areas.⁹

The national plan of action for the girl child (1991-2000):

The plan of action is to ensure survival, protection and development of the girl child in order to safeguard the bright future of the girl child.

National policy for the women empowerment (2001): The Department of women and child development in the Ministry of Human Resource Development prepared a “National Policy for the Women Empowerment” in the year 2001. The goal of this policy was to bring about the advancement, development and empowerment of women.¹⁰

Conclusion

In order to enhance women empowerment nationally and internationally the insistence on gender equality in recruitment, selection, salary, free education and management support at office is needed. Constitution provides a few safety measures, still women are understood to be in insecure environment.. The constitutional privileges must also be available in corporate sector as well. The problem in the country is serious about the women belonging to disadvantaged groups. They are the most exploited lot. The Social activist should keep a vigil on the atrocities committed on women belonging to weaker sections and help them to fight the legal battle for obtaining justice. Schemes need to be introduced for helping women who are victims of marital violence, who are deserted and those engaged in sex professions. . The female literacy rate is also lower than the male literacy rate. The reality is deprivation and exploitation of women especially women from rural areas and those belonging to deprived sections of the society remain affected despite government and NGOs initiative for women empowerment.

Creating awareness among women especially belonging to weaker sections about their rights is the need of the hour. Government has to be vigilant for ensuring that there is no discrimination against the girl child and her rights are protected. The social stigma like child marriage, female foeticide, child abuse and child prostitution must be eradicated immediately. The Empowerment of women has become one of the most important concerns of 21st century not only at national level but also at the international level. Efforts by the Government are to ensure Gender equality but Government initiatives alone would not be sufficient to achieve this goal. Society must take initiative to create a climate in which there is no gender discrimination and women have full opportunities of self decision making and participating in the social, political and Economic life of the Country with a sense of equality. Empowerment of women is not for individual women alone but to all women groups and it also to the families and communities as a whole through collective action for development.

Bibliography

1. Towards Equality, The Unfinished Agenda - Status of Women in India, 2001, Report by National Commission for Women , India
2. Guidelines on Women's Empowerment by United Nations [Online] <http://www.un.org/popin/unfpa/taskforce/guide/iatfwemp.gdl.html>
3. Forbes, Geraldine H: "Women in Modern India", Cambridge University Press
4. Kabeer, Naila, "Reflections on the measurement of women's empowerment" In *Discussing Women's Empowerment - Theory and Practice*, 2001 Sida Studies No.3 Novum Grafiska AB: Stockholm.
5. Search for a vision statement on women's empowerment (2002) National Commission for Women, New Delhi
6. Rajni Kashyap, "Empowerment and Status of Women in Modern India" Prajwal Books, Delhi
7. Flavia Agnes "Women & Law in India", 2004 Oxford University Press, New Delhi
8. J.P. Bhatnagar, "Law Relating Women & their Rights", Second Edition 1999, Asoka Law House, New Delhi
9. Dr. S.R.Myneni, "Women & Law", Asia Law House, Hyderabad Empowerment of Women the Most Effective Tool, Press Release by Secretary General, United Nations <http://www.un.org/News/Press/docs/sgsm9738.doc.htm>
10. Dr. S.R.Myneni, "Women & Law", Asia Law House, Hyderabad Empowerment of Women the Most Effective Tool, Press Release by Secretary General, United Nations <http://www.un.org/News/Press/docs/sgsm9738.doc.htm>

Web Sources

1. <http://www.iipa.org.in/New%20Folder/16--Sunita.pdf>
2. <https://www.termpaperwarehouse.com/essay-on/Women-Empowerment/361052>
3. <https://www.wikigender.org/wiki/indian-laws-relating-to-women-and-children/>
4. http://mospi.nic.in/sites/default/files/reports_and_publication/statistical_publication/social_statistics/WM16ConstitutionalLegalRights.pdf
5. <https://www.termpaperwarehouse.com/essay-on/Women-Empowerment/361052>
6. <https://www.slideserve.com/harshapopat210/why-is-there-still-a-need-for-women-empowerment>